

The Role of Autogenous Bone Grafts in Maxillofacial Reconstruction : A Literature Review

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Abstract

Maxillofacial reconstruction often requires the use of bone grafts to restore form and function following trauma, tumor resection, or congenital defects. Autogenous bone grafts, obtained from the patient's own skeletal tissue, are considered the gold standard for reconstructive procedures in the maxillofacial region. This review examines the current evidence on the application of autogenous bone grafts in maxillofacial reconstruction. The review explores the biological properties and advantages of autogenous bone grafts, including their osteogenic, osteoinductive, and osteoconductive capabilities. It also discusses the various donor sites commonly used for harvesting autologous bone, such as the iliac crest, calvarium, and intraoral sites, and compares their clinical outcomes and morbidity profiles. Furthermore, the review highlights the use of autogenous bone grafts in specific maxillofacial reconstructive procedures, including alveolar ridge augmentation, sinus floor elevation, reconstruction of mandibular and maxillary defects, and craniofacial deformities. The integration of autologous bone grafts with other materials, such as barrier membranes and growth factors, is also examined. The review concludes by discussing the current limitations, challenges, and future trends in the use of autogenous bone grafts for maxillofacial reconstruction and findings also provide valuable insights for clinicians and researchers in the field of oral and maxillofacial surgery.

Keywords : Maxillofacial reconstruction, autogenous bone grafts, osteoinduction, alveolar ridge augmentation, barrier membranes, growth factors, bone tissue engineering

Introduction

Advanced techniques for treating diseases like jaw tumors, mouth malignancies, congenital abnormalities, and traumatic injuries like fractures are all included in maxillofacial surgery. From minor periodontal problems to intricate segmental jaw deformities requiring the restoration of mechanical function and facial attractiveness, bone grafting is essential for rebuilding these defects.

Allogenic, autologous, or synthetic bone transplants are essential for supporting structural integrity and bone regeneration. The proper integration of a graft depends on methods such as osteoconduction and osteoinduction, which direct the formation of new bone.

Microvascular surgery is one of the latest developments, improving results with accurate soft tissue and bone repair. Adequate vascular supply, infection management, and patient-specific characteristics including health and nutritional state are

also important success factors.

In general, successful maxillofacial reconstruction seeks to return bone integrity, facial dimensions, and functional results customized to each patient's requirements. This all-encompassing strategy highlights the continuous improvements in surgical methods and patient care in this specialized area.^[1-3]

Discussion

Autogenous Grafts

When utilizing autologous bone grafting, the recipient of the graft's bone is used for the transplant. Since the bone used in this technique comes from the patient, there is less chance of graft rejection, which makes it the ideal option for block graft procedures. Because they are osteoind-

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uctive, osteogenic, and osteoconductive, autologous grafts encourage the formation and fusion of new bone tissue. But one disadvantage of autologous grafts is that they require a second surgical site, which may cause discomfort after the procedure. A blood supply is necessary for every bone graft at the transplant site. To achieve sufficient vascularization, more blood vessels may need to be added to the donor bone and periosteum, depending on the size and location of the graft. With this kind of transplant, the periosteum and related blood arteries, in addition to donor bone, are necessary. This type of graft is referred to as an essential bone graft.^[4]

Classification

Classification According To Its Use In Maxillofacial Surgery

Calvarial Bone Graft

- **Cranial bone chips**
 - Alveolar bone reconstruction (adolescent repair)
 - Alveolar cleft
 - Outer table of the cranium reconstruction
- **Outer table partial thickness/potato chip graft**
 - Orbital wall
 - Orbital floor
- **Outer table full thickness**
 - Facial Augmentation
- **Inner table or full thickness graft**
 - Mandibular contour defects
 - Defects of the mentum
 - Zygoma/malar eminence reconstruction
 - Total zygomatic deformities reconstruction (Trea-cher Collins syndrome)
 - TMJ Reconstruction
- **Costochondral Graft**
 - Zygomatic arch
 - TMJ Reconstruction
 - Ear Reconstruction

ILIAC Bone Graft

- **Iliac bone chips**
 - Alveolar bone reconstruction(newborn)
- **Non-vascularised iliac graft (Anterior/Posterior)**
 - Full thickness defects of mandible
 - Vertical mandibular asymmetry
 - TMJ Reconstruction
- **Vascularised iliac graft (Anterior/Posterior)**
 - Mandibular reconstruction

Scapular Flaps

- Class Ia and IIb Maxillary defect
- Orbital
- Maxillary sinus front wall
- Large craniofacial defects.
- **Tibial Bone Graft**
 - Pathology defect
 - Sinus Augmentation
 - Alveolar cleft

- Continuity defect of mandible

Fibular Myocutaneous Flaps

- **Non-vascularised**
- **Vascularised**
 - Craniofacial cancer defect reconstruction
 - External orbit
 - Zygoma
 - Condyle
 - Mandible
 - Class II Maxillary defect
 - TMJ Reconstruction

Calvarial Bone Graft

Craniofacial bone grafting is pivotal for reconstructing defects in the craniofacial skeleton, with surgeons generally agreeing that facial bone defects should be addressed with bone grafts and soft tissue defects with soft tissue reconstruction.

Cranial bone grafts are widely favoured among craniofacial surgeons globally due to their reliability and effectiveness. They are considered the gold standard for craniofacial reconstruction, particularly when excluding vascularized free bone flaps and nonvascularized iliac bone grafts used in mandibular reconstruction. Composed of membranous bone, cranial grafts are believed to maintain their volume better than other types, especially when securely fixed due to their rigid nature.

The cranial vault is increasingly preferred as a bone donor site due to its proximity to the surgical area, ease of access for harvesting, and ample bone availability. This makes it particularly suitable for various applications such as repairing orbital defects, filling osteotomy gaps, and reconstructing facial cleft deformities. The dense cortical consistency of cranial bone and its robust haversian network facilitate rapid revascularization and minimal resorption, making it ideal for reshaping the craniomaxillofacial skeleton.

Advantages of cranial bone grafts include their excellent integration, minimal post-operative pain, and absence of visible scarring. However, limitations include the risk associated withthin calvarial bones less than 5mm, which heightens the potential for dural or cerebral injury. Additionally, they are not recommended for cases with significant sagittal misalignment between the maxilla and mandible.^[5]

Figure 1 Scalp Dissection With Self Retained Retractors In Place

Figure 2 Multiple struts of corticocancellous bone removed from the outer table of the skull

Figure 3 Intraoperative view of the cranial vault following removal of several split thickness grafts.

Costochondral Rib Graft

Costochondral rib grafts are crucial in mandibular reconstruction, particularly for rebuilding the temporomandibular joint. They mimic the size of the native condyle and their cartilaginous covering supports continued growth, preventing ankylosis at the skull base. This procedure aims to restore ramus length, vertical face height, occlusion, and normal TMJ function, essential for mastication, speech, and growth in children.^[6]

When a child has active growth centers, the temporomandibular joint (TMJ) is rebuilt using costochondral rib grafts to treat deformities caused by rheumatoid arthritis, trauma, neoplasms, infections, and congenital dysplasias. When other treatments are not appropriate, they treat adult patients with rheumatoid arthritis, osteoarthritis, and idiopathic condylar resorption that causes TMJ problems. They are also used in cranioplasty, craniomaxillofacial defect reconstruction, nasal dorsum defect correction (saddle nose abnormalities), and costochondral cartilage rebuilding of the ear's helical framework. Recent pulmonary infections, cardiac instability, and a history of restrictive lung disease are all contraindications because they increase risk during surgery and recovery.^[7]

Figure 4 : Rib Graft Figure

5 : Removal of Rib

Iliac Bone Graft

Because autogenous grafts combine structural support with all three of the characteristics of a bone graft—osteogenic, osteoconductive, and osteoinductive—they remain safe and widely used.^[8,9]

The best source of autogenous bone transplant is iliac crest bone graft (ICBG).^[10] The iliac crest can be used to harvest both cancellous alone and tricortical transplants.^[11,12] Whereas posterior ICBG is obtained for posterior spinal fusion surgeries, anterior ICBG is taken for anterior procedures such as anterior cervical corpectomy and fusion (ACCF) and anterior cervical discectomy and fusion (ACDF).^[13-15] We outline the advantages of this method of ICBG harvesting over the traditional approach for patients undergoing ACDF/ACCF.

Figure 8. 10 Incision Site For The Posterior Iliac Crest

Figure 8.11 A Full-thickness Flap, Including The Dorsolumbar Fascia Gluteus Maximus Muscle, And Periosteum, Is Elevated To Expose The Outer Cortex Of The Posterior Ilium.

Anterior Iliac Graft

Key landmarks are noted and the patient is put supine with the hip raised. A lateral incision is made around 2 cm above the iliac crest, starting from above the external iliac vessels. Palpation of the iliac crest and anterior superior iliac spine is used to advise the location of the incision. The incision is placed laterally and inferiorly to lessen pain following surgery along the beltline.

A 4- to 6-cm incision is made along the iliac crest, obliquely aligned, 1-2 cm posterior to the iliac tubercle and 1 cm inferior to the anterior superior iliac spine. The lateral femoral cutaneous nerves, subcostal, and iliohypogastric nerves are circumvented by this method.

An osteotome is used to harvest the corticocancellous block graft, and hemostasis is established before the abdominal wall layers are carefully closed. In order to relieve pain, drains and an epidural catheter are inserted, and the skin is sealed with clips.^[16]

Posterioriliacrest

The patient is placed in a prone posture with 20° of reverse hip flexion, and bone landmarks are highlighted using a hip roll. The superior and middle cluneal nerves are not cut; instead, the incision is made over the gluteus maximus insertion, a triangular fossa.

In order to avoid the cluneal nerves, a 6-to 8-cm curvilinear incision is made after the posterior ilium, centered above the gluteus maximus insertion. The incision goes to the gluteal crease 3 cm laterally and paramedianly. The gluteus medius is gently reflected for more exposure after the lumbodorsal fascia is transected and lifted to reveal the posterior iliac crest.

On the posterior iliac crest, a 5.5 cm osteotomy is done, with additional cancellous bone removed using curettes, following the ridge of the gluteus maximus insertion. Bone wax or collagen is used to produce hemostasis, and the skin, subcutaneous tissue, lumbodorsal fascia, and periosteal layer are closed. To avoid aspirating the marrow, a drain is frequently set to low suction^[17]

Scapular Flap

The descending branch of the circumflex scapula artery is used in the parascapular flap, which Nassif first described in 1982. Teot et al. initially demonstrated harvesting the scapula's lateral border on this artery, and they also showed that both the parascapular and scapula flaps, supplied by this artery, could be elevated simultaneously.^[18]

Using skin paddles aligned with the transverse or descending branch of the CSA, flap elevation is performed on a prone or lateral decubitus patient. Outlining the scapular flap involves maintaining margins of 2 cm around important features. Above the triangle where the CSA flows, the lateral skin paddle needs to be drawn. The scapular lateral border is where bone is removed, and the flap width should be between 8 and 10 cm. In order to elevate the skin paddle, dissection is carried out medially to laterally, detaching the flap from the underlying muscles until the CSA is reached and exposed.

The CSA's deep segment exhibits three branches that reach the proximal lateral edge of the scapula in the close-up view. For the skin paddles, the cutaneous branch splits into descending and horizontal branches. The infraspinatus and teres minor muscles are sliced 3 cm parallel to the lateral border in order to gain access to the scapular bone. A muscle cuff is left in place. Up to the bone feeders, the muscle is completely transected from the inferior angle.^[17]

Reconstructing complex midfacial abnormalities of the orbit, maxilla, skull base, and mandible is accomplished with the use of the chimera flap.^[19] It is appropriate for older patients with vascular problems and has minimal donor site morbidity, good scarring, thin, hairless skin, low risk of peripheral vascular disease, and reasonable bone quality. It also permits the use of numerous separate skin paddles. But the quality of the bone is not as good as with DCIA or fibula flaps, and the patient must be repositioned, making it impossible for two teams to operate simultaneously. Furthermore, simultaneous flap harvesting and ablation are not possible.^[20]

Figure 8 : Flap Location

Figure 9 : Elevation of Parascapular Skin Paddle

Free fibula flap

For free-flap mandible repair, the fibula is the chosen donor site because of its uniform shape, sufficient length, and low donor-site morbidity. It can be elevated with a skin island for composite-tissue repair and permits a two-team approach.^[21]

Using bone holding forceps, the distal cut end of the fibula is gently dragged out to expose the interosseous border. In order to preserve neurovascular structures, a periosteal stripper is subsequently inserted, leaving the anterior slit laterally and the circular stripper medially. To prevent traction damage to the neurovascular structures, the periosteum is gently rotated around the fibula, especially the medial section that is merged with the interosseous membrane. To reduce neurovascular injury, the graft is administered through the distal incision and rotated to guarantee dissociation from surrounding tissues. Range-of-motion exercises for the knees and ankles are performed after a compression bandage with a plaster slab is worn for a maximum of two weeks. Depending on the wound, gradual weight-bearing is allowed after three to four weeks.^[22]

Reconstructing significant defects following oncologic surgery, trauma, or congenital anomalies-especially in the maxilla and mandible-are among the Indications for the fibula flap. It provides enough bone for dental implants, a lengthy bone segment, a dependable skin paddle, and possible innervation. Contraindications include hypercoagulable states, medical illnesses such as vasculitis, connective tissue disorders, and peripheral vascular disease, as well as circumstances not appropriate for prolonged surgery. Implications may include nerve injury, numbness, blood vessel damage, muscular weakness, compartment syndrome, ankle instability, infection, persistent discomfort, and even limb loss.^[23-26]

Conclusion

The best option for correcting bone abnormalities in oral and maxillofacial, spinal, and trauma operations is autogenous bone transplants; the graft location is chosen based on anatomical considerations and individual requirements. Understanding the dangers of autogenous bone harvesting, including uncommon but serious consequences, is still essential even when bone substitutes are becoming more widely used. Vascularized bone flaps are especially useful in maxillofacial reconstruction because they can tolerate masticatory stresses and adequately repair the oromandibular complex, even in damaged areas. Donor sites such the scapula, iliac crest, and fibula offer sufficient soft tissue for covering and enough bone for implants; the osteocutaneous flap in the fibula is the most versatile. Novelties such as the double free flap with tensor fascia-lata, the pedicled myoosseous flap with a free skin flap.

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